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Academic Integrity - Plagiarism

summary

Author: [Aday Amirbekov](#)

Affiliation: [Technical University of Liberec](#)

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What is Plagiarism?

“*Plagiarize* (and *plagiarism*) comes from the Latin *plagiarius* “kidnapper.” This word, derived from the Latin *plaga* (“a net used by hunters to catch game”), extended its meaning in Latin to include a person who stole the words, rather than the children, of another. When *plagiarius* first entered English in the form *plagiary*, it kept its original reference to kidnapping, a sense that is now quite obsolete.” (Merriam-Webster dictionary, Accessed 4 Apr.2024)

“Taking over the ideas, methods, or written words of another, without acknowledgment and with the intention that they be taken as the work of the deceiver.” (“Statement on Plagiarism,” 1989).

“Plagiarism is the appropriation of another person’s ideas, processes, results, or words without giving appropriate credit, including those obtained through confidential review of others’ research proposals and manuscripts.” (Office of Science and Technology Policy, 1999)

Basically, plagiarism is the act of using someone else's work or ideas without giving proper credit to the original author or creator. This can include copying text, images, music, and other creative works and presenting them as one's own. Plagiarism is considered unethical and can have serious consequences in academic, professional, and artistic fields.

Image 1 Plagiarism. Image created with AI tool DALL-E-3, prompt: Idea stealing, 2024-04-04, <https://poe.com/DALL-E-3>

Types of Plagiarism

According to (Roig, 2014) there are different types of plagiarism, including verbatim plagiarism, mosaic plagiarism, and insufficient acknowledgment. These forms of plagiarism can have severe consequences, ranging from receiving a failing grade on an assignment to expulsion from an academic institution.

Efforts to categorize various forms of plagiarism have been made by researchers including (Lancaster, 2003; Stein, 2007). However, these categorizations typically focus on different facets, such as comparing plagiarism from a single source versus multiple sources, or distinguishing between intrinsic and extrinsic plagiarism.

“One important form of plagiarism that can often be found in countries with a national language other than English is translations. Paraphrasing can also be broken down into different forms, and there are specific kinds of plagiarism that have only rather recently been named” (Debora Weber-Wulff, 2014). Which includes: synonym replacement, changing sentence structure, combining information, dividing information, using different modality or perspective, spinbotting.

In the website of plagiarism checking tool iThenticate they demonstrate the research infographic about 10 types of plagiarism in research (Image 2). In this chapter, we discuss a more comprehensive classification of plagiarism suggested by sources mentioned above.

Image 2 Types of Plagiarism in Research. Image taken from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230923132326/https://www.ithenticate.com/resources/infographics/types-of-plagiarism-research>. Accessed at 2024-04-04.

Copy & Paste

Also called as Verbatim Plagiarism. This sort of plagiarism is the easiest to commit—by simply highlighting a part of text from the internet (or an entire page) and hitting two keyboard sequences (CTRL + C and CTRL + V), one may swiftly construct a copy and paste it into a new document.

Mosaic Plagiarism

Also known as Shake & Paste Collections, sometimes called “patch writing”. This method is to craft a plagiarized paper involves extracting material from multiple sources and mixing them together. These copied segments are then haphazardly pieced together, typically without any coherent sequence. This approach can create the impression that the paragraphs were randomly mixed together like in a bag, shaken up, and then randomly drawn out for assembly in the document.

Self Plagiarism

Also known as Duplication or Repetitive Research. This phenomenon occurs when a researcher recycles content from their own prior work and integrates it into new studies or papers without proper citation. The ethic of such self-duplication is a contentious topic, and the acceptability often hinges on the content that has been replicated.

Paraphrasing

Also known as Structural Plagiarism. It involves a plagiarist rephrasing another author's work without providing appropriate attribution. This type of plagiarism may encompass adopting the original work's argumentative framework, utilizing sources in the same sequence as they appear in the source material, copying footnotes, mirroring the experimental design, or replicating the research objective, all without acknowledging the original creator.

Pawn Sacrifice Plagiarism

This type of plagiarism where “the source citation is either given in a footnote or only listed in the bibliography. It is not made clear, however, exactly how much has been taken” (Debora Weber-Wulff, 2014, see Lahusen 2006).

AI-Plagiarism

AI-generated plagiarism refers to the act of using artificial intelligence tools, like advanced language models, to create content that is then presented as one's own original work without proper attribution, which can violate ethical standards and

intellectual property rights. As AI technology becomes more sophisticated and widely accessible, concerns about its role in facilitating plagiarism have increased.

As AI continues to advance, the conversation around AI plagiarism is likely to evolve, requiring ongoing dialogue and adjustments in legal, academic, and professional spheres to address the new challenges it presents. “The main complication introduced by the advent of chatGPT, then, is the degree to which such AI programs can source ideas from unpublished sources on the internet without attribution; it is unclear at this point whether a fix is possible.” (Dien, 2023).

The Technical University of Liberec (TUL) is actively adapting to the challenges posed by artificial intelligence (AI) tools in academia, particularly in preventing new forms of plagiarism. TUL has established clear guidelines that mandate the explicit disclosure of AI tool usage in academic work, emphasizing the author's responsibility for the integrity and correctness of their output. This directive also includes critical evaluation of AI-generated content, recognizing the potential for outdated or biased data influences. Furthermore, TUL encourages educators to integrate AI tool usage into curricula while also setting strict rules against its use in knowledge verification during exams unless specified otherwise. These strategies ensure that the use of AI complements educational goals while maintaining academic integrity (Technical University of Liberec, 2023).

Image 3 Copy and paste. Image created with AI tool DALL-E-3, prompt: CTRL + C and CTRL + V, 2024-04-04, <https://poe.com/DALL-E-3>

More types of plagiarism discussed here: [17 Common Types of Plagiarism](#), [The Plagiarism Spectrum](#).

Why it Happens

The motivations behind plagiarism are varied and can stem from several factors, including:

- **Pressure to Succeed:** Students or academics may feel intense pressure to achieve high grades or publish work, leading them to plagiarize in order to meet expectations or deadlines.

- **Lack of Understanding:** Some individuals may not fully understand what constitutes plagiarism, including the nuances of paraphrasing and proper citation (Sokol et al., 2022).
- **Poor Time Management:** Procrastination or poor planning can lead to a situation where there is not enough time to complete an assignment properly, tempting an individual to plagiarize (Nonis and Swift, 2001).
- **Lack of Confidence:** A lack of confidence in one's own writing ability or subject knowledge may lead a person to plagiarize, believing they cannot produce quality work on their own (Wajekar et al., 2018).
- **Cultural Differences:** There may be different understandings of plagiarism and intellectual property in different cultures, which can lead to unintentional plagiarism (Hayes and Introna, 2005).
- **Unintentional:** Sometimes plagiarism occurs by mistake, such as when a person forgets to cite a source or improperly paraphrases without giving credit.
- **Accessibility of Information:** The vast amount of information available online can make it easy to copy and paste text, making plagiarism seem like an easy option.
- **Perceived Low Risk of Detection:** If individuals believe they are unlikely to be caught, they may be more willing to plagiarize.
- **Lack of Integrity or Ethical Understanding:** Some individuals may not value the ethical considerations against misrepresenting someone else's work as their own (Bebeau, 1994).
- **Habitual Behavior:** Once an individual successfully plagiarizes without repercussions, they may be more likely to do it again (Stone et al., 2009).

Consequences

Academic Consequences (McCabe et al., 1999):

- **Disciplinary Action:** Students caught plagiarizing may face disciplinary action from their educational institution, which can include a written warning,

mandatory completion of a course on academic integrity, or more severe penalties.

- Failed Assignments or Courses: Plagiarized work is often given a failing grade, which can impact a student's overall academic performance and progress.
- Suspension or Expulsion: In cases of severe or repeated plagiarism, a student may be suspended or expelled from their educational institution.
- Revoked Scholarships or Awards: Students who plagiarize may lose scholarships, awards, or honors that were granted based on academic performance or integrity.

Professional Consequences (Martin, 1994):

- Damaged Reputation: Being caught plagiarizing can tarnish a person's reputation, making it difficult to gain trust from peers, supervisors, and professional communities.
- Loss of Job or Career Opportunities: Plagiarism can lead to termination of employment, especially in academic, research, and writing-related fields, and can hinder future job prospects.
- Legal Repercussions: If the plagiarized content is copyrighted, the original author may take legal action against the plagiarist, which can result in fines or other legal penalties.

Legal Consequences (Standler, 2012):

- Copyright Infringement: Plagiarism may involve the unauthorized use of copyrighted material, which is a legal offense and can result in lawsuits, fines, or orders to pay damages. Current copyright laws may not fully address the nuances of AI-generated content, leading to potential legal grey areas regarding ownership and infringement.
- Defamation: If plagiarism involves the unauthorized use or alteration of someone's work in a way that harms their reputation, it could potentially lead to defamation claims.

Personal and Ethical Consequences (John M. Braxton and Alan E. Bayer, 1999; Park, 2003):

- Loss of Personal Integrity: Committing plagiarism undermines an individual's personal ethics and integrity, which can lead to a loss of self-respect and the respect of others.
- Eroded Moral Standards: Engaging in plagiarism can contribute to a broader erosion of moral and ethical standards within academic and professional communities.

Other Consequences:

- **Withdrawal of Published Work:** If plagiarism is discovered in published work, the piece may be retracted, which can have lasting negative effects on an individual's professional standing.
- **Academic Record Notation:** Some institutions note acts of academic dishonesty on a student's official transcript, which can affect graduate school admissions or employment.

Image 4 Plagiarism consequences. Image created with AI tool DALL-E-3, prompt: sad student behind the cage animation, 2024-04-04, <https://poe.com/DALL-E-3>

How to Stop Plagiarism?

Publishers such as Elsevier and Springer are escalating their efforts against plagiarism by adopting Similarity Check, a sophisticated software for detecting plagiarized content in academic submissions (Butler, 2010).

Image 5. I must not copy. Image created with AI tool DALL-E-3, prompt: Student seating and typing in computer: I must not copy (illustration), 2024-04-04, <https://poe.com/DALL-E-3>. The idea was taken from illustration by [PETE ELLIS/DRAWGOOD.com](https://www.petellis.com/).

Halting plagiarism involves a combination of education, ethical training, the use of technology, and the implementation of clear policies and consequences. Here are several strategies that can help prevent plagiarism:

Educational Interventions:

- **Raise Awareness:** Educate students and professionals about what constitutes plagiarism and why it is a serious issue.
- **Instruction on Proper Citation:** Teach proper citation methods and the importance of giving credit to original sources. It's crucial to educate users about ethical practices when using AI tools, emphasizing the importance of original work and proper attribution.

- Emphasize Original Thought: Encourage original thinking and the development of individual ideas to reduce the temptation to copy others' work.
- Develop Research Skills: Offer training on conducting research, taking notes, and synthesizing information to reduce the reliance on source material.

Policy and Ethical Framework:

- Clear Policies: Establish clear, accessible, and well-communicated policies regarding academic integrity and the consequences of plagiarism.
- Honor Codes: Implement honor codes that require students to pledge not to commit plagiarism and to report any observed instances of it.
- Ethics Training: Include ethics as part of the curriculum to emphasize the importance of integrity in academic and professional life.

Technological Tools:

- Plagiarism Detection Software: Use tools like Turnitin, Grammarly, or Copyscape to detect potential plagiarism in written work.
- Secure Assessments: Employ secure testing environments and question randomization to reduce the opportunity for cheating on assessments.

Assignment Design:

- Unique and Creative Assignments: Design assignments that require personal reflection or unique perspectives that are less likely to be found in existing sources.
- Process-Oriented Assignments: Break larger assignments into stages (proposal, bibliography, draft, final paper) and evaluate each part to monitor the progression of students' work.
- Oral Presentations: Require students to present their work and discuss their research process to ensure they understand and can articulate what they have written.

Institutional Support:

- Access to Resources: Provide ample resources such as writing centers and libraries to support students in their academic work.
- Small Class Sizes: Smaller class sizes can allow for more interaction and personalized feedback, reducing the likelihood of plagiarism.
- Professional Development: Offer ongoing professional development for educators on how to detect and prevent plagiarism.

Personal Accountability:

- Self-Checks: Encourage the use of self-check plagiarism tools by students and professionals before submitting any work.
- Peer Review: Incorporate peer review in the classroom so students can learn from one another and spot potential plagiarism early.

In this article from [Nature](#) ten experts provide strategies for eradicating the duplications (“How to stop plagiarism,” 2012).

Plagiarism Detection Tools

Plagiarism detection tools are software applications designed to identify instances of copied content and help maintain academic integrity. They compare submitted texts against a vast database of published work, including academic papers, books, articles, and content available on the internet. Here are some widely used plagiarism detection tools:

1. [Turnitin](#): A popular tool among academic institutions, Turnitin checks submissions against its extensive database of academic papers, web pages, and a repository of previously submitted work.
2. [Grammarly](#): While primarily a grammar and spell-check tool, Grammarly also offers a plagiarism detection feature that checks your text against billions of web pages.
3. [Copyscape](#): A web-based plagiarism detection service that is commonly used by content creators, website owners, and marketers to check the uniqueness of website content.
4. [Plagscan](#): An online service that allows you to check documents for plagiarism, targeting academic institutions and businesses.
5. [Unicheck](#): This tool is designed for both educational institutions and individuals, offering plagiarism detection and a focus on privacy and data security.
6. [Quetext](#): A plagiarism detection tool that includes a deep search technology, which is designed to identify more sophisticated forms of plagiarism.
7. [PlagiarismCheck.org](#): Aimed at educators and students, it helps in checking papers for plagiarism, offering detailed reports.
8. [iThenticate](#): Primarily used by researchers and professional writers, iThenticate compares submissions to a large database of scholarly content.

9. [Viper](#): A free plagiarism checker that scans against essays, journals, and other sources published on the internet.
10. [Plagiarism Detector](#): This tool checks for plagiarism by comparing texts against a wide range of search engines and databases. Free to use up to 1000 words.
11. [ProWritingAid](#): Alongside writing enhancement tools, it provides a plagiarism check feature that compares your writing to millions of published works.
12. [DupliChecker](#): A free online plagiarism detection service up to 1000 words that allows users to check for duplicate content.

Several studies have been conducted to assess the effectiveness of different plagiarism detection tools. Jiffriya et al., 2013 discussed various text-based plagiarism detection tools, such as Dupli Checker, Article Checker, Anti-P, Plagiarism Checker X, Turnitin, and Ferret, emphasizing their capabilities in detecting intra-corporal and extra-corporal plagiarism. Furthermore, Khaled and Al-Tamimi, 2021 provided an overview of plagiarism detection methods and tools, categorizing them based on plagiarism processes, classification, and datasets used. Mostofa et al., 2021 analyzed researchers' awareness of plagiarism and the impact of plagiarism detection tools on preventing plagiarism, underscoring the significance of these tools in promoting ethical research practices. A recent study compared the performance of four paid plagiarism detection tools in identifying plagiarism in AI-generated articles, suggesting that cost-effective solutions may be viable for researchers seeking such software (Anil et al., 2023).

Note: Artificial intelligence tools were used for writing this summary, specifically DALL-E-3 for image creation, scite_ for research and text writing, and ChatGPT-4 for drafting and text enhancement.

If you encounter any citations that are incorrect or notice any that might be missing in this article, I would greatly appreciate it if you could kindly bring them to my attention so that I can promptly address and rectify the issue.

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